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Figure 1. 1701-M, June 3, 4:24 p.m. 2017, estimated age three years, location, Silver Gate.

Figure 2. 1701-M, June 3, 2017, Silver Gate.

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Figure 3. 1701-M June 3, 2017, Silver Gate.

Figure 4. 1701-M June 3, 2017, Silver Gate.

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Also seen June 5, 7:51 p.m. 2017, Warm Creek Trail Head.

June 7, 7:26 p.m. 2017, Warm Creek Trail Head.

June 8, 8:41 p.m. 2017, Barronette peaks.

June 13, 7:49 p.m. 2017, Soda Butte Creek picnic area.

June 17, 9:30 p.m. 2017, Warm Creek area.

Figure 5. 1701-M Sept. 12, 7:50 a.m. 2017, Warm Creek area.

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Figure 6. 1701-M June 10, 5:50 p.m. 2018, Warm Creek area.

Figure 7. 1701-M June 10, 2018, Warm Creek Area.

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Figure 8. 1701-M June 10, 2018, Warm Creek Area.

Figure 9. 1701-M June 10, 2018, Warm Creek Area.

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Figure 10. 1701-M Oct 15, 2018, Round Prairie area.

Figure 11. 1701-M Oct 16, 7:55 a.m. 2018, (on the left), seen sparring with 1710 M (on the right)
Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow area.

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Figure 12. 1701-M Oct 18, 8:07 a.m. 2018, (on the far right) Seen with 1710-M, 1806-F and 1808-C Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 13. 1701-M Sept 26, 6:41 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadows.

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Figure 14. 1701-M June 15, 4:57 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 15. 1701-M June 15, 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadows.

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Figure 16. 1701-M Oct 17, 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 18. 1702-F July 11, 9:23 p.m. 2017, with calf 1723-C Soda Butte Picnic Area.

Figure 19. 1702-F June 24, 2017, with calf 1723-C Lower Barronette Peaks Meadows.

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Figure 20. 1702-F June 21, 2018, Warm Creek, no calf.

Figure 21. 1702-F June 21, 2018, Warm Creek, no calf.

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Figure 22. 1702-F June 23, 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 23. 1702-F June 26, 2018, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow with calf 1823-C.

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Figure 24. 1702-F June 29, 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow with calf 1823-C.

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Figure 25. 1703-F June 2, 2017, Trout Lake Trailhead area Round Prairie with calf 1711-C.

Figure 26. 1703-F June 8, 6:28 a.m. 2018, approximately one mile southwest of Warm Creek.

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Figure 27. 1703-F June 8, 6:28 a.m. 2018, seen each day, same location, June 2 through June 9.

figure 28. 1703-F June 8, 6:28 a.m. 2018.

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Figure 29. 1703-F June 8, 6:28 a.m. 2018.

Figure 30. 1703-F June 8, 6:28 a.m. 2018.

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Figure 31. 1703-F June 9, 8:27 a.m. 2018, at the bridge over Soda Butte Creek 2 km west of Warm Creek.

Figure 32. 1703-F June 9, 8:27 a.m. 2018.

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Figure 33. 1703-F June 2, 2019, Warm Creek, cause of death breached fetus.

Figure 34. 1703-F June 2, 2019, Warm Creek.

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Figure 35. 1704-M June 5, 7:51 p.m. 2017, Warm Creek Trailhead.

Also seen June 7, 2017, Warm Creek Trailhead,

June 7 7:34 p.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow,

June 12 6:36 p.m. 2017, Upper Barronette Peaks Meadow.

June 14 8:00 p.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 36. 1704-M Sept 12, 8:30 a.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

Figure 37. 1704-M Sept 12, 8:30 a.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

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Figure 37. 1704-M June 4, 2018, Silver Gate.

Figure 38. 1704-M June 10, 6:16 p.m. 2019, Pebble Creek Camp Ground.

Also sighted June 9, 6:12 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow, no photo.

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Figure 39. 1704-M June 10, 6:16 p.m. 2019, Pebble Creek Camp Ground.

Figure 40. 1704-M October 3, 7:55 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie seen with 1710-M, lower right.

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Figure 41. 1704-M October 3, 7:55 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie.

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Figure 42. 1705-F June 1, 2017, Upper Barronette Peak Meadow estimated age two years.

Figure 43 1705-F June 1, 2017, Upper Barronette Peak Meadow seen with twin 1706-F on right.

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Figure 43. 1705-F June 23, 12:37 2017 p.m. Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

Figure 44 1705-F July 7, 5:58 a.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow seen with 1706-F and 1709-M.

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Figure 45. 1705-F July 11, 9:23 a.m. 2017, Soda Butte Picnic Area.

Figure 46. 1705-F July 1, 1 9:23 a.m. 2017, Soda Butte Picnic Area.

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Figure 47. 1705-F July 11, 9:23 a.m. 2017, Soda Butte Picnic Area.

Figure 48. 1705-F July 20, 2017, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

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Figure 49. 1705-F July 20, 2017, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

Figure 50. 1705-F September 3, 7:00 a.m. 2017. at the bridge over Soda Butte Creek 2 km West of Warm Creek.

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Figure 51. 1705-F September 3, 2017, Pebble Creek Picnic Area.

Figure 52. 1705-F September 3, 2017, Pebble Creek Picnic Area.

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Figure 53. 1705-F September 5, 2017, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

Figure 54. 1705-F September 5, 2017, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

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Figure 55. 1705-F September 5, 2017, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

Figure 56. 1705-F September 5, 2017, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

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Figure 57. 1705-F June 21, 4:03 p.m. 2019, Silver Gate. Seen with calves 1924-C and 1925-C.

Figure 58 1705-F June 21 4:03 p.m. 2019 Silvergate. Seen with calves 1924-C and 1925-C.

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Figure 59. 1705-F June 22, 2019, NE Entrance area. No calves sighted.

Figure 60. 1705-F June 26, 2019, Pebble Creek Picnic Area. No calves sighted.

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Figure 61. 1705-F June 26, 2019, Pebble Creek Picnic Area. No calves sighted.

Figure 62. 1705-F June 29, 2019, Pebble Creek Picnic Area. No calves sighted.

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Figure 63. 1705-F July 4, 5:42 a.m. 2019. Pebble Creek Camp Ground, no calves sighted.

Figure 64. 1705-F Sept 24, 6:21 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie. Single calf sighted.

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Figure 65. 1705-F Sept 24 6:21 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie, with a single calf.

Figure 66. 1705-F (right) sept 24 6:21 a.m. Round Prairie, with calf (left) designated 1924-C

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Figure 67. 1706-F June 1, 9:23 a.m. 2017, (on the right) Upper Barronette Peaks Meadows.

Estimated age 12 months, seen with her twin 1705-F (on the left). The two can be easily distinguished because 1706-F has fewer tumors and a more pronounced bell than 1705-F.

Figure 68. 1706-M July 11, 9:23 a.m. 2017.

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Figure 69. 1706-F July 11, 2017.

Figure 70. 1706-M July 11, 2017.

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Also sighted July 20, 8:22 a.m. Lower Barronette Peaks meadow, both animals sighted.

July 20, 9:30 p.m. Lower Barronette Peaks meadow, Both animals sighted.

July 23 6:53 a.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks meadow, both animals sighted.

Figure 71. 1706-F July 23, 6:53 a.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 72. 1706-F July 23, 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Also sighted July 29, 8:30 p.m. Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow, no photo.

July 30, 7:30 a.m. Soda Butte Picnic area, both animals sighted, no photo.

Aug 31, 7:30 a.m. Lower Barronette Peaks Meadows Both animals sighted no photo.

Figure 73. 1706-F and 1705-F Sept 3, 7:00 a.m. 2017, Soda Butte Creek near Upper Barronette Peaks.

Figure 74. 1706-F Sept 5, 7:15 a.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 75. 1706-F Sept 5, 2017.

1706-F not sighted in 2018.

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Figure 76. 1706-F June 3, 8:25 a.m. 2019, NE Entrance area.

Figure 77. 1706-F June 6, 5:09 a.m. 2019, Pebble Creek Camp Ground area.

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Figure 78. 1706-F June 14, 5:04 a.m. 2019, Pebble Creek Campground.

Figure 79. 1706-F June 15, 5:00 a.m. 2019 Pebble Creek Campground.

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Figure 80. 1706-F June 16, 8:06 a.m. 2019 Pebble Creek Campground.

Figure 81. 1706-F June 16, 2019, Pebble Creek Campground.

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Figure 81. 1706-F June 16, 2019, Pebble Creek Campground.

June 19, 9:07 a.m. 2019, no photo.

Figure 82. 1706-F July 9, 7:40 a.m. 2019

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Figure 83. 1706-F July 9, 7:40 a.m. 2019.

Figure 84. 1706-F July 18, 5:47 p.m. 2019, Pebble Creek Picnic area.

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Figure 85. 1706-F July 18, 5:47 p.m. 2019, Pebble Creek Picnic area.

Figure 86. 1706-F July 19, 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 87. 1706-F July 19, 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 89. 1706-F July 24, 6:35 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 90. 1706-F July 27, 5:29 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Also seen Aug 12, Aug 19, and Sept 3, 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow, no photos.

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Previously, in 2017, designated 1708-C

Figure 90. 1708-M June 2, 2017, Silver Gate Estimated age 12 months.

Figure 91. 1708-M June 2, 2017.

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Figure 92. 1708-M June 2, 2017.

Figure 93. 1708-M June 2, 2017.

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Figure 94. 1708-M June 2, 2017.

Figure 95. 1708-M June 26, 7:25 a.m. 2018, Warm Creek Picnic area.

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Figure 96. 1708-M June 17, 6:44 a.m. 2019, Warm Creek Picnic area.

Figure 97. 1708-M June 17, 2019.

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Figure 98. 1708-M June 22, 7:47 a.m. 2019, sighted with unidentified cow.

Figure 99. 1708-M July 8, 4:59 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie, sighted with unidentified cow.

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Figure 100. 1708-M July 8, 2019, left side of photo.

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Figure 101. 1709-M July 7, 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Seen with 1705-F and 1706-F.

Figure 102. 1709-M July 25, 2017, Circle Prairie area.

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Figure 103. 1709-M June 28, 6:25 a.m. 2018, Circle Prairie area.

Figure 104. 1709-M July 8, 7:23 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 105. 1709-M July 8, 7:23 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 105. 1709-M July 8, 7:23 a.m. Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 106. 1709-M Oct 10, 9:29 a.m. 2018, Round Prairie.

Figure 107. 1709-M Oct 10, 9:29 a.m. 2018, Round Prairie.

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Figure 108. 1709-M July 10, 5:54 a.m. 2019, Warm Creek Picnic Area.

Figure 109. 1709-M July 10, 5:54 a.m. 2019, Warm Creek Picnic Area.

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Figure 110. 1709-M July 10, 5:54 a.m. 2019, Warm Creek Picnic Area.

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Figure 111. 1710-M June 5, 8:47 a.m. 2017, Warm Creek Trailhead.

1710-M is the dominant bull in the area.

Figure 112. 1710-M June 5, 8:47 a.m. 2017, Warm Creek Trailhead.

June 6, 7:56 a.m. 2017, Warm Creek Trailhead, no photo.

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July 7, 5:43 a.m. 2017, Warm Creek Trailhead, no photo.

Figure 113. 1710-M Sept. 13, 2017, Round Prairie.

Figure 114. 1710-M Sept 13, 2017, Round Prairie.

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Figure 115. 1710-M Sept 24, 2017, Pebble Creek Camp Ground area.

Figure 116. 1710-M June 10, 5:46 p.m. 2018, Warm Creek Trail Head.

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Figure 117. 1710-M June 10, 5:46 p.m. 2018, Warm Creek Trail Head.

Figure 118. 1710-M Oct. 11 1:22 pm 2018 Pebble Creek Picnic area.

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Figure 119. 1710-M Oct. 11, 1:22 p.m. 2018, Pebble Creek Picnic area.

Figure 120. 1710-M Oct. 13, 8:42 a.m. 2018, NE Entrance area.

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Figure 121. 1710-M (right) Oct. 16, 7:55 a.m. 2018, Round Prairie.

Figure 122. 1710-M Oct. 16, 6:54 p.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 123. 1710-M (2nd from the left) Oct. 18, 8:07 am 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow. Seen with 1808-C (far left) 1806-F (2nd from the right) and 1701-M (far right).

Figure 124. 1710-M Oct. 19, 8:11 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 125. 1710-M Sept 23, 6:23 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie.

Figure 126. 1710-M Sept. 24, 6:18 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie area.

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Sept. 28 7:20 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie, no photo.

Figure 127 1710-M Oct. 1, 7:25 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie area.

Figure 128. 1710-M Oct. 2, 7:36 a.m. 2019, Pebble Creek Campground area.

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Figure 129. 1710-M Oct. 3, 7:36 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie.

1710-M seen Oct. 7, 7:33 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie, no photo.

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Figure 130. 1711-C (left) seen with 1703-F (right) June 2, 2017. Round Prairie, Trout Lake Trailhead area. Sighted each day June 2, through 8, 2017.

Figure 131. 1711-C June 2, 2017.

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Figure 132. 1711-C June 2, 2017.

Figure 233. 1711-C June 9, 2017, Silver Gate area.

Subject 1711-C was not sited again and is presumed deceased as of June 9, 2017.

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Figure 133. 1712-M June 11, 8:25 a.m. 2017, Barronette Peaks Area.

Figure 134. 1712-M June 14, 7:48 a.m. Warm Creek Area.

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Figure 135. 1712-M July 20, 5:45 a.m. 2017, Pebble Creek Campground area.

Figure 136. 1712-M July 20, 5:45 a.m. 2017, Pebble Creek Campground area.

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Subject 1716-F with fraternal twin 1717-M and calves 1824-C and 1828 C

Figure 137. 1716-F July 19, 9:28 a.m. 2017, Church area.

Estimated age 13 months. Subject shows signs of significant infection of suspected PV while 1717-M shows no signs, although the two remain in extremely close proximity.

Figure 138. 1716-F July 19, 9:28 a.m. 2017, Church area.

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Figure 139. 1716-F (right) with 1717-M (left) July 19, 9:28 a.m. 2017, Church area.

Figure 140. 1716-F (left) with 1717-M (right) July 19, 9:28 a.m. 2017, Church area.

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June 8, 8:00 a.m. 2018, Pebble Creek Picnic Area sighted with calf designated 1824-C, no photo. June 9, 2018, same area, no photo.

Figure 141. 1716-F June 11, 2018, 1716-F with calf 1824-C Pebble Creek Picnic Area.

Figure 142. 1716-F June 11, 2018.

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Figure 143. 1716-F June 12, 2018, with calf 1824-C.

Figure 144. 1716-F June 12, 2018.

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Figure 145. 1716-F June 18, 5:12 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Subject appears to have a foreign object stuck in her bell.

Figure 146. 1716-F June 23, 8:19 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Subject appears to have shed the foreign object stuck in her bell.

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Figure 147. 1716-F June 26, 8:23 a.m. 2019 NE Entrance area.

Subject sighted with calf designated 1928-C. This was the only observation of 1928-C and it is presumed the calf died sometime between June 26 8:23 am 2019 and the next sighting, July 4 6:32 am 2019.

Figure 148. 1716-F July 4, 6:32 a.m. 2019, NE Entrance area. No calf sighted.

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Figure 151. 1717-M July 19, 9:28 p.m. 2017, Silver Gate.

1717-M (left) seen with his paternal twin 1716-F (right). Estimated age 13 months. No signs of tumors or blemishes indicative of PV despite living in close proximity with his heavily infected sibling.

Figure 152. 1717-M July 19, 9:28 p.m. 2017, Silver Gate.

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Figure 153. 1717-M Aug 22, 2017, Warm Creek area.

Figure 154. 1717-M Aug 22, 2017, Warm Creek area.

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Figure 155. 1717-M Sept. 13, 2017, seen with 1710-M (front) and 1704-M (rear, left).

Figure 156. 1717-M June 17, 6:17 a.m. 2019. Pebble Creek area.

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Figure 157. 1717-M June 17, 6:17 a.m. 2019, Pebble Creek area.

Figure 158. 1717-M June 17, 6:17 a.m. 2019, Pebble Creek area.

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Subject 1718-F, 1720-C 1929-C and 1930-C

Figure 159. 1718-F July 23, 9:30 p.m. 2017, Warm Creek Picnic area.

Figure 160. 1718-F July 23, 9:30 p.m. 2017, Warm Creek Picnic area.

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Figure 161. 1718-F with calf 1720-C Sept. 8, 8:00 a.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 162. 1718-F (background) with calf 1720-C (foreground) Sept 8, 8:00 a.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 163. 1718-F seen with calves 1929-C and 1930-C, July 6, 5:11 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

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Figure 164. 1719-F Sept. 13, 2017, Round Prairie area.

Figure 165. 1719-F Oct. 16, 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Subject is easily identified by a clipped left ear and pronounced withers.

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Figure 166. 1719-F Oct. 11, 7:18 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie.

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Figure 177. 1720-C (left) with cow 1718-F (right) Sept 8, 8:00 a.m. 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 178 1720-C Sept 8, 8:00 a.m. Lower Barronette Peaks meadow.

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Figure 167. 1721-M June 15, 2017, Warm Creek area.

Figure 168. 1721-M Oct. 15, 8:33 a.m. 2017, Round Prairie area.

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Figure 169. 1721-M June 13, 2018, Warm Creek area.

Figure 170. 1721-M June 13, 2018, Warm Creek area.

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Figure 171. 1721-M Oct. 2, 7:42 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 172. 1721-M Oct 9, 9:24 a.m. 2018, Trout Lake Trailhead area.

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Figure 173. 1721-M June 15, 3:39 p.m. 2019, Warm Creek area.

Figure 174. 1721-M June 15, 3:39 p.m. 2019, Warm Creek area.

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Figure 175. 1721-M Oct. 11, 6:28 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie area.

Figure 176. 1721-M (right) Oct 11, 6:28 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie area. Seen with 1933-M (left).

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Figure 179. 1723-C (left) seen with 1702-F (right) July 11, 9:23 p.m. 2017, Soda Butte Picnic Area.

Figure 180. 1723-C (left) June 24, 2017, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 181. 1802-M and 1803-M June 8, 6:00 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Subjects were only sighted once and the photographic evidence was insufficient to distinguish the individuals.

Figure 182. June 23, 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 183. 1802-M or 1803-M not sure which but it's one of them. June 23, 2018, Pebble Creek Picnic Area.

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Figure 184. 1806-F June 24, 8:26 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 185. 1806-F June 24, 8:26 a.m. 2018 Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 186. 1806-F June 26, 5:50 a.m. 2018, Barronette Peaks Meadow area.

Figure 187. 1806-F 6:40 am June 26, 2018, Barronette Peaks area.

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Figure 188. 1806-F (behind) with calf 1808-C (in front) Sept. 12, 7:02 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 189. 1806-F with 1808-C 1806-F with 1808-C Sept. 12, 7:02 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 190. 1808-C Sept. 15, 7:12 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 191. 1806-F Sept 15, 7:12 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 192. 1806-F with 1808-C Sept 15, 7:12 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 193. 1806-F (front) 1808-C, Sept 15, 7:12 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 194. 1808-C (center) with 1806-F (right) Sept 15, 7:12 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow. Also seen Sept. 17, and 20, and Oct. 16, same location, no photos.

Figure 195. 1806-F (far left) with 1808-C (second from the left) 1710-M (second from the right) and 1721-M, Oct 18, 8:12 a.m. 2018.

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Figure 196. 1806-F Oct. 19, 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Area.

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Figure 197. 1812-M July 2, 5:54 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

Seen with paternal female twin 1813-F. Neither show any signs of potential PV. Estimated age 14 months.

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Figure 198. 1813-F July 2, 5:40 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Observed with paternal twin 1812-M. Neither show signs of suspected PV. Subject can be identified but a scar over her left eye and another under her left ear.

Figure 199. 1813-F July 2, 5:40 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 200. 1813-F July 2, 5:40 a.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 201. 1813-F May 31, 8:54 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

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Figure 202. 1813-F, May 31, 8:54 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

Figure 203. 1813-F (left), with 1908-C (right) June 1, 9:30 a.m. 2019, Pebble Creek Picnic Area.

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Figure 204. 1813-F June 5, 6:18 a.m. 2019 NE Entrance.

Figure 205. 1813-F June 15, 4:29 p.m. NE Entrance area.

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Figure 206. 1213-F (right) with calf 1908-C (left) June 21, 6:23 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

Figure 207. 1213-F June 21, 6:23 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

Photo adjusted to show the scar over her left eye.

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Figure 208. 1813-F (right) with calf 1908-C (left) Sept. 21, 6:20 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

Figure 209. 1813-F (right) with calf 1908-C (left) Sept. 11, 6:20 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

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Figure 210. 1213-F Sept. 11, 6:20 a.m. Silver Gate.

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Figure 211. 1814-M Sept 20, 7:36 p.m. 2018, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 212. 1814-M Sept. 20, 7:36, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 213. 1814-M Oct. 19, 2018, Silver Gate.

Figure 214. 1814-M June 3, 5:11 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 215. 1814-M. June 3, 5:11 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 216. 1814-M June 6, 5:02 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 217. 1814-M June 22, 6:44 a.m. 2019, Church area.

Figure 218. 1814-M Sept. 25, 6:38 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

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Figure 219. 1814-M Sept. 30, 6:42 p.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

Figure 220. 1814-M Sept, 30, 6:42 p.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peaks Meadow.

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Figure 221. 1816-M Sept. 14, 7:55 a.m. 2018, Circle Prairie area.

Subject identified by an abbreviated bell a single left eyebrow tine and a split right eyebrow tine.

Figure 222. 1816-M Sept. 14, 7:55 a.m. 2018, circle Prairie area.

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Figure 223. 1816-M Sept. 14, 7:55 a.m. 2018, Circle Prairie area.

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Figure 224. 1902-F June 1, 7:43 am, 2019. Silver Gate, estimated age 12 months.

Figure 225. 1902-F June 1, 7:43 am, 2019, Silver Gate.

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Figure 226. 1902-F June 1, 7:43 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

Subject seen in very close proximity to 1903-M 1904-F 1910-M, 1905-C and 1906-C. Based on proximity and similarity in features I'd say 1902-F, 1903-M and 1910-M are triplets recently rejected by 1904-F, who has two calves of the year.

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Figure 227. 1903-M June 1, 7:45 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate estimated age 12 months.

Seen with his twin 1302-F in close proximity to 1904-F and her calves of the year 1905-C and 1906-C.

Figure 228. 1903-M June 1, 7:45 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

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Figure 229. 1904-F (left) with 1905-C and 1906-C June 1, 7:45 a.m. 2019 Silver Gate.

Subject is easily identified by a clipped right ear and a unique bell configuration. The two Calves are thus far indistinguishable.

Figure 230. 1904-F June 1, 7:45 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

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Figure 231. 1904-F with calf. June 5, 6:54 a.m. 2019, NE Entrance area, both calves sighted.

Figure 232. 1904-F with calves, June 7, 10:48 a.m. 2019, NE Entrance area.

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Figure 233. 1904-F June 12, 5:41 a.m. Pebble Creek Picnic Area, both calves sighted.

Figure 234. 1904-F Oct. 6, 9:03 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate. Only one calf observed designated 1905-C.

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Figure 235. 1905-C Oct. 6, 9:03 a.m. 2019 Silver Gate. 1905-C is female.

Figure 236. 1905-C, Oct 6, 9:03 a.m. 2019 Silver Gate.

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Figure 237. 1904-F (right) and 1905-C (left), Oct 6, 9:03 a.m. 2019, Silver Gate.

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Figure 238. 1910-M Yearling (left side of photo) June 3 5:30 a.m. 2019 Silver Gate.

Subject appears indistinguishable from 1902 F and 1903 M. So much so that I suspect they're triplets. Subject seen above interacting closely with 1903 M. All three are yearlings.

Appendix C

Figure 239. 1910-M June 5 5:35 a.m. 2019 N.E. Entrance area

Figure 240. 1910-M June 5 5:35 a.m. 2019 N.E. Entrance area.

Appendix C

Figure 241. 1910-M June 9 12:05 p.m. 2019 Silver Gate.

Figure 242. 1910-M June 13 6:29 a.m. 2019 Warm Creek area.

Appendix C

Figure 243. 1912-M June 4 7:45 a.m. 2019 Pebble Creek Camp Ground.

Figure 243. Flipped and enlarged

Subject can be distinguished from 1919-M by his antler development .

Appendix C

Figure 244. Subject 1919-M June 17, 6:17 a.m. 2019, Pebble Creek .

Figure 245. Subject 1919-M June 17, 6:17 a.m. 2019, Pebble Creek.

Subject has a similar dewlap to 1912-M but can be distinguished by less developed antlers

Appendix C

Figure 246. Subject 1919-M June 17, 6:17 a.m. 2019, Pebble Creek.

Figure 246. Subject 1919-M June 17, 6:17 a.m. 2019, Pebble Creek.

Appendix C

Figure 247. June 21 10:00 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

Figure 248. June 21 10:00 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

Appendix C

Figure 249. June 21 10:00 a.m. 2019, Lower Barronette Peak Meadow.

Appendix C

Figure 250. 1926-F July 5, 6:18 a.m. 2019, Warm Creek Trailhead.

Figure 251. 1926-F July 5, 6:18 a.m. 2019, Warm Creek Trailhead.

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Figure 252. 1926-F July 5, 6:18 a.m. 2019, Warm Creek Trailhead.

Figure 253. 1926-F with 1927-C July 5, 6:18 a.m. 2019, Warm Creek Trailhead.

Appendix C

Figure 254. 1926-F July 5, 6:18 a.m. 2019, Warm Creek Trailhead.

Figure 255. 1926-F July 5, 6:18 a.m. 2019, Warm Creek Trailhead.

Appendix C

Figure 256. 1931-M (right) July 8, 5:46 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie seen with 1813-F.

1931-M bears a strong resemblance to 1812-M and these two could be the same animal.

Figure 257. 1931-M (left) July 8, 5:46 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie seen with 1813-F.

Appendix C

Figure 258. 1932-M Sept. 3, 6:02 a.m. 2019, Church area.

Subject is missing his antlers and part of his left ear.

Figure 259. 1932-M Sept. 3, 6:02 a.m. 2019, Church area.

Appendix C

Figure 260. 1932-M Sept. 3, 6:02 a.m. 2019, Church area.

Figure 261. 1932-M Sept. 10, 6:56 a.m. Round Prairie

Appendix C

Figure 262. 1932-M Sept. 24, 6:10 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie.

Figure 263. 1932-M Sept. 24, 6:10 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie.

He challenged 1710-M and was chased away

Appendix C

Figure 264. 1932-M (left) Sept. 24, 6:10 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie.

Figure 265. 1932-M (left) Oct. 2, 7:38 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie.

Appendix C

Figure 266. 1932-M (left) Oct. 7, 7:12 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie.

Appendix C

Figure 267. 1933-M (left) Oct. 7, 7:28 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie.

Seen with 1710-M and seemed to be mimicking his rutting behaviors but not challenging.

Figure 268. 1933-M (left) Oct. 11, 6:31 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie

Seen with 1721-M, estimated age 16 to 20 months.

Appendix C

figure 269. 1933-M Oct. 11, 6:31 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie

figure 270. 1933-M Oct. 11, 6:31 a.m. 2019, Round Prairie